

Methodologies of research on competition activity in volleyball

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Introduction: Studying the competition activity of volleyball players in a thorough and step-by-step manner makes it possible to develop an adequate system of training of athletes. On the basis of the said knowledge, it is possible not only to make detailed plans and increase the effectiveness of training of athletes, but also to manage the team correctly during a game (adjust the strategy and tactics in a timely manner). Success of a team in a competition depends on all of these components.

The **analysis** of the game actions of volleyball players was conducted according to four most important indicators. These include activity (volume), effectiveness, win, and defeat at the time of performing various technical-tactical actions by players of the team.

For **evaluating the competition activity** of athletes, we have developed a methodology designed to evaluate the quality of performance of skills of the game with a four-symbol system.

Each technical-tactical action of an athlete is evaluated at the moment of performance of the skill according to **criteria** developed by us.

The **analysis** of the game actions of volleyball players was conducted according to four most important indicators developed by us. These include activity (volume), effectiveness, win, and defeat at the time of performing various technical-tactical actions by players of the team.

Keywords: Volleyball, competition, analyzing, criteria.

საშეჯიბრო მოღვაწეობის კვლევის მეთოდოკები ფრენბურთში

გენადი გიკაშვილი

პროფესორი, საქართველო, თბილისი, ილია ჭავჭავაძის გამზ. 49

საქართველოს სახელმწიფო სპორტის უნივერსიტეტი

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აბსტრაქტი: ფრენბურთელთა საშეჯიბრო მოღვაწეობის საგულდაგულო და გეგმაზომიერი შესწავლა სპორტსმენტა მომზადების ადეკვატური სისტემის შემუშავების საშუალებას იძლევა. აღნიშნული ცოდნის ბაზაზე შესაძლებელია არა მხოლოდ სპორტსმენტა მრავალწლიანი მომზადების ეფექტურობის გაზრდა და დეტალური დაგეგმვა, არამედ გუნდის სწორი მართვა (სტრატეგიისა და ტაქტიკის დროული კორექცია) უშუალოდ თამაშის მსვლელობისას. ყველა აღნიშნულ კომპონენტზე დამოკიდებულია შეჯიბრში გუნდის წარმატებული გამოსვლა.

ფრენბურთელთა სათამაშო მოქმედების **ანალიზი** ტარდებოდა ოთხი ყველაზე მნიშვნელოვანი მაჩვენებლების მიხედვით. მათ მიეკუთვნება: აქტიურობა (მოცულობა), ეფექტურობა, შედეგიანობა და წაგება გუნდის მოთამაშეების მიერ სხვადასხვა ტექნიკურ-ტაქტიკური მოქმედების შესრულების დროს.

სპორტსმენების საშეჯიბრო მოღვაწეობის შეფასებისთვის ჩვენს მიერ შემუშავებულ იქნა ისეთი მეთოდოლოგია, რომელიც ისახავს თამაშის ილეთების შესრულების ხარისხის ოთხნიშნა პირობით შეფასებას.

სპორტსმენის თითოეული ტექნიკურ-ტაქტიკური მოქმედების შეფასება წარმოებს ილეთის შესრულების მომენტში ჩვენს მიერ შემუშავებული კრიტერიუმების შესაბამისად.

ფრენბურთელთა სათამაშო მოქმედების ანალიზი ტარდებოდა ჩვენს მიერ შემუშავებულ ოთხი ყველაზე მნიშვნელოვანი მაჩვენებლების მიხედვით. მათ მიეკუთვნება: აქტიურობა (მოცულობა), ეფექტურობა, შედეგიანობა და წაგება გუნდის მოთამაშეების მიერ სხვადასხვა ტექნიკურ-ტაქტიკური მოქმედების შესრულების დროს.

საკვანძო სიტყვები: ფრენბურთი, შეჯიბრი, ანალიზი, კრიტერიუმები.

Introduction: Studying the competition activity of volleyball players in a thorough and step-by-step manner makes it possible to develop an adequate system of training of athletes. On the basis of the said knowledge, it is possible not only to make detailed plans and increase the effectiveness of training of athletes, but also to manage the team correctly during a game (adjust the strategy and tactics in a timely manner). Success of a team in a competition depends on all of these components [1, 2, 3, 5, 6].

Methods: Analysis of scientific-methodological literature; questionnaire survey of leading specialists; method of pedagogical observation; mathematical statistical method.

Findings of the study and discussion: The competition activity of volleyball players was **registered** during matches, by one observer who recorded all the actions on a voice recorder (one after the other). The following aspects were registered during the competition activity of volleyball players:

1. Score of the game (before playing off a score);
2. Version of performance of a skill;
3. Evaluation of performance of a skill;
4. Place of performance of a skill (zone of the court);
5. Time breaks;
6. Changes in the line-up of the team;
7. Numbers of players.

During the recording process, the following actions were documented: during **attack** – serve, pass, spike; during **defense** – reception of passes, reception of spikes, blocking, and cover [1, 2, 4].

It should also be noted that, in our methodology, the evaluation of reception of passes and reception of spikes are dealt with separately as independent skills. It is impermissible to unite these technical-tactical actions under the topic of “playing in defense” due to different figures of the speed of the ball’s movement, angle of attack (trajectory of the ball’s movement), distance from the player receiving the ball, and duration of the ball’s flight [2, 6, 7].

After the match was over, we moved the records in the same order to a special report. Then we processed the information using statistical methods.

For **evaluating the competition activity** of athletes, we developed a methodology that is designed to evaluate the quality of performance of skills with a four-symbol system [3, 7].

The fact that the methodology uses a small number of evaluations makes it significantly easier to use it in practice. At the same time, it gives us enough information about athletes’ actions in their training and competition activity [5].

Each technical-tactical action of an athlete is evaluated at the moment of performance of the skill in accordance with **criteria** that we developed [6].

The four-symbol evaluation used in relation to each skill contained some differences, although its essence remained the same:

The evaluation "⊕" was written for an ideal performance of a skill. For example: A score has been won at the time of the serve.

The evaluation "+" was written for a good performance of a skill. For example: The rival's actions have been extremely restricted.

The evaluation "-" was written for a bad performance of a skill. For example: The rival's actions have not been restricted; they have good opportunities to develop the attack combination.

The evaluation "⊖" was written for a mistake – a score has been lost.

The four-symbol evaluation used in relation to each skill had precise **criteria** listed below [1, 2, 6].

At the time of a serve:

"⊕" – A score has been won;

"+" – The serve has complicated the rival's action; the rival is restricted in developing a desired successful attack;

"–" – The serve has not complicated the rival's action, the rival has a good opportunity to develop an attack and performs a second pass near the net;

"⊖" – A mistake at the time of the serve (the ball has been sent into the net, outside the court, etc.).

At the time of a spike:

"⊕" – A score has been won and the right to serve has been obtained;

"+" – The ball remains in the game after attack, but the rival's next action has been hindered, or the attacking team has the opportunity to set the ball again;

"–" – The ball remains in the game after the attack; the rival has the opportunity to develop the attack combination;

"⊖" – The ball has been lost.

At the time of performing a second pass:

"⊕" – A pass to hit, without a block;

"+" – A pass to hit, against one block;

"–" – A pass to hit, against two blocks;

"⊖" – A pass to hit, against three blocks.

At the time of receiving a serve:

"⊕" – The ball has been redirected accurately for performing a spike;

"+" – The ball has been redirected accurately to the setter;

"–" – The reception has complicated the action of the setter, an attack combination cannot develop;

"⊖" – A mistake – a score has been lost.

At the time of receiving a spike:

"⊕"

- " " – The ball has been redirected accurately to the setter;
- " + " – The reception has complicated the action of the setter, an attack combination cannot develop;
- " – " – After the reception, the ball went to the rival's side, or a second pass was performed by another player (not the setter), or the ball was taken to the rival's side due to inability to process it;
- "⊖" – A mistake – a score has been lost.

At the time of blocking:

- "⊕" – A score has been won;
- " + " – The block has blocked the way of the ball, or the ball remaining in the game has not complicated the rival's action, or it has created suitable conditions for the team performing the block to develop the attack;
- " – " – The block has weakened the hit, but the next action has been made difficult;
- "⊖" – A mistake – a score has been lost.

At the time of a cover:

- "⊕" – The place of the cover has been selected correctly, the ball has been sent accurately to the setter;
- " + " – The action of the setter has been complicated;
- " – " – The action of teammates has been complicated, it is necessary to send the ball to the rival's side;
- "⊖" – A mistake – a score has been lost.

The **analysis** of the game actions of volleyball players was conducted according to four most important indicators. These include activity (volume), effectiveness, win, and defeat at the time of performing various technical-tactical actions by players of the team [7].

Using these indicators, we determined the quality of performance of skills by individual players and the number of skills performed, as well as the characteristics of game actions of the team [10,18].

Activity (Volume) (V), or the volume of performance of technical-tactical actions, is the number of skills performed or imitated by a player (team) during one game, a certain segment, a match or a competition. This indicator can also be used in the analysis of physical loading of athletes during training sessions and competition activity.

Effectiveness (E) is the percentage ratio of all actions evaluated by the sums of " + " and " – " to the volume of performed actions (V). It is a qualitative characteristic of the technical-tactical mastery of athletes and is represented by the following formula:

$$E = \frac{(\sum \text{"⊕"}) + (\sum \text{" + "})}{V} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Win (W) is the percentage ratio of actions evaluated by the sign ⊕ " " to the volume of performed actions (V). It is also a qualitative characteristic of the technical-tactical mastery of athletes and is represented by the following formula:

$$W = \frac{(\sum \text{" } \oplus \text{ "})}{V} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

Defeat (D) is the percentage ratio of actions evaluated by the sign ⊖ of " " to the volume of all performed actions (V). It is also an indicator of the technical-tactical mastery of athletes and is represented by the following formula:

$$D = \frac{(\sum \text{" } \ominus \text{ "})}{V} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

Using these indicators, we determined the quality of performance of individual skills as well as the characteristics of game actions of individual players and the team.

Conclusions:

1. For **evaluating the competition activity** of athletes, we have developed a methodology designed to evaluate the quality of performance of skills of the game with a four-symbol system.
2. Each technical-tactical action of an athlete is evaluated at the moment of performance of the skill according to **criteria** developed by us.
3. The **analysis** of the game actions of volleyball players was conducted according to four most important indicators developed by us. These include activity (volume), effectiveness, win, and defeat at the time of performing various technical-tactical actions by players of the team.
4. Using these indicators, we determined the quality of performance of skills by individual players and the number of the skills performed, as well as the characteristics of game actions of the team.

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